

Türkiye Eastern Century

Abdullah KONTE

To cite this article: Abdullah KONTE, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-6, 2023, p. 01 – 15. - 0099-0001-2306-0501.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver ...") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Author(s) Name Surname: Abdullah KONTE

University: Uludag University

Department: FEAS International Relations Department

Title: Accounting Specialist

Date: June 2023

Summary

The concept of Eurasianism in Turkey and Russia is a complex and multifaceted concept shaped by various historical and cultural factors. The development of the Ottoman Empire is a concept influenced by various factors such as the rise of the Ottoman Empire, the rise of the Ottoman Empire, and the rise of the Neo-Algerian Empire. The concept of Eurasianism, a concept rooted in the concept of "Eurasia" and "anti-Western" in Turkey and Russia, has become a central aspect of the Turkish and European political and cultural landscape. It is identical with a central concept in the development of the concept of "Eurasia" and the concept of "West" in various countries such as Turkey, Kazakhstan, Turkey, Azerbaijan and Turkey. The concept of Eurasianism is a central aspect of the Turkish and Russian political and cultural landscape, rooted in the Neo-Algerian tradition.

Limitedness

the subject in the light of world literature and data . The research was limited to closely related author and literature topics. Restricted by literature review.

Notifications

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial Disclosure: The authors reported no use of financial support for this article.

Ethical Statement

Publication ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others, and works for the realization of these principles in the field of related sciences.

Abstract

In both Turkey and Russia, the idea of Eurasianism is a complicated and diverse term that has been molded by a variety of historical and cultural elements. The expansion of the Ottoman Empire is a notion that was shaped by a number of different circumstances, including the growth of the Ottoman Empire, the establishment of the Neo-Algerian Empire, and the rise of the Ottoman Empire. The idea of Eurasianism, which originates from the concepts of "Eurasia" and "anti-Western" in Turkey and Russia, has emerged as an essential component of the political and cultural landscape in both Turkey and Europe. It is the same as a fundamental idea that contributed to the formation of the concepts of "Eurasia" and "West" in a number of nations, including Turkey, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, and Turkey, among others. The ideology of Eurasianism, which has its origins in the Neo-Algerian tradition, has become an essential component of the political and cultural environment in both Turkey and Russia. With its origins in the notion of the "West" and the concept of "Eurasia" as a core concept in the development of Turkish and Russian politics, the concept of Eurasianism is also a central part of the political and cultural landscape in Turkey and Russia. Eurasianism is also a central aspect of the cultural landscape in Turkey and Russia. As a consequence of this, the idea of Eurasianism in Turkey and Russia has been formed by a variety of causes, such as the expansion of the Ottoman Empire, the creation of the New Algerian Empire, the growth of New Algeria, and the development of New Algeria's political and political ties. Cultural landscapes with its origins

2

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177)

8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

in the Ottoman Empire and its role as an influential factor in the formation of the political and cultural landscapes in both Turkey and Russia, the idea of Eurasianism has highlighted a fundamental component of both countries' political and cultural environments.

Keywords: *Eurasianism, Turkey and the East, Political and Cultural Synthesis, Turkish History and the East*

Introduction

Without taking into account the Eurasianism philosophy, a complete comprehension of it is impossible. Eurasianism has emerged as a potential strategic refuge in recent years due to the growing anti-Western sentiment and mistrust in Turkey and Russia. Eurasianism has occasionally been a tactical refuge, despite the fact that the Eurasian region is seen as an area of struggle between Turkey and Russia. Eurasia is the geography of international politics for Russia. It is also an alternative western culture and civilization center for Turkey. For the west, Eurasia is viewed as a strategic territory relating to natural resources, energy, and energy corridors. The geographical notion referred to as "Eurasia" may be simplified to its most fundamental level by stating that the continents of Asia and Europe each make up an equal portion of the overall whole. Additionally accountable for the formation of an ideology was the concept of Eurasia, which served as a geographical framework. This school of thought, which is also known as Eurasianism, had a significant position in the intellectual history of Russia. Neo-Eurasianism is one of the expressions of this philosophy that is still important in current times. Neo-Eurasianism is a term that was coined in the late 19th century.

Even though Russia had a negative view of Turkey due to the Eurasian ideology of the USSR, the growing anti-Western attitude in Turkey opened new avenues of collaboration between Russia and Turkey. This occurred despite the fact that Russia had a negative image of Turkey. This was the case regardless of the fact that the Russians held an unfavorable view of Turkey.

Findings

Neo Eurasia by Aleksandr Dugin, answer to the question:

"During the 1980s, when the Soviet Union first started to fall apart, we Neo-Eurasians came to the realization that this notion was absolutely suitable for the age in which we now find

3

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.

ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE
TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177)
8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

CURRENT SCIENCE

ourselves... In particular, we were of the opinion that this idea was completely applicable to the epoch in which we currently find ourselves... The perspectives held by the early Eurasians and Gumilev, neo-It served as the foundation for the growth of the Eurasianism movement. (...) The need of Turkey and Russia working together to address the challenges posed by Eurasianism was once again highlighted by this ideology. It should not just exist as an idea from the past; if we could come to an agreement on this matter, I would appreciate it; it should have occurred in partnership with the people of Kazakhstan, Turkey, Azerbaijan, and Turkish countries; but, it did not. should be instantly applicable.

The political strategist Aleksandr Dugin develops the concept of Eurasianist even further, and this is the path that Russia needs to adopt today. He believes that by absorbing the allied periphery nations that are grouped around this center region, Russia would be able to extend its influence in the region and become a worldwide force.

There is no distinction to be drawn between the people of North Korea developing nuclear weapons against their adversaries when they are unable to satisfy their fundamental necessities and the Turkish government's decision to make significant investments in the country's military sector despite the country's deteriorating economic circumstances. The acceptance of the society by sacrificing their own personal living comfort with UAVs and SHAs; the only variation is the amount of authoritarianism that is practiced. It cannot be denied that Turkey, both socially and politically, is one step closer to becoming a member of the Eastern Bloc than it was the day before.

Dou Perinçek group is the first commercial enterprise established in Turkey

The "Eurasian Conference," the first iteration of which was held in 1996, did not garner a great deal of public interest. A total of around 31 nations have dispatched delegates, which is a rather low amount. Additionally, Suleyman Demirel was a participant in the "Second Eurasian Conference" that took place in the year 2000. This meeting is producing a significant amount of background noise. National Security Council Secretary General Tuncer Kilic stated in 2002 during a seminar that was conducted at the War Academy that "Turkey does not receive support from the EU in matters concerning its national interests, and it includes Turkey, Russia, and Iran, without ignoring the United States."

Literature Review

Former MGK During his time as Secretary General of the NSC, Tuncer KILIN gained a reputation for being the person who first proposed the concept of building alliances with China, Russia, Iran, and Syria. KILIN was noted for this. This was a fundamental principle that guided his approach to political theory. The United States learned about him as a result of his criticism of the Greater Middle East Project and his assertion that the North Atlantic Treaty Organization had gone beyond its bounds in terms of both its commitments and its goals. He is well-known for holding opinions that go counter to the global interests of both the United States of America and Israel. He regularly made remarks in his surroundings that were critical of NATO, the United States of America, and the European Union.

The challenge of maintaining the Ottoman state was the impetus for the first steps in the direction of westernization. The Ottoman society itself is the root of the issue, and the process of westernization is a continual endeavor to remedy the social problems that have been created as a result. This process, which began with the Tanzimat, led in the notion that creative initiatives in the political-military sector could not be effective and that the state could not be rescued. This notion gained weight prior to social transformation. Elimination of the political, economic, and military deficiencies of the Ottoman Empire; Westernization, in combination with the fact that it was founded on the defects in society, was regarded as a force that would bring competition to the state in the face of issues and inadequacies.

Patrick Wintour, a contributor to the publication The Guardian, wrote an essay in which he discussed the "Eurasianist" circle that Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan maintains. He drew attention to the group by stating that the powerful Eurasian team that Erdogan was leading was in favor of breaking away from the EU. Wintour was making a reference to Erdogan's advocacy for withdrawing from the EU.

According to what was written by Patrick Wintour, "Turkey itself is split within itself. A powerful Eurasia-based organization revolves around Erdogan; this group has been antagonistic against Erdogan for many years and does not feel thankful to Turkey for sheltering millions of Syrian migrants. Others are advocating for withdrawal from the EU. The modernization of the economy is one example.

CURRENT SCIENCE

As soon as the Republic was officially established, conflicts and competing interest groups between society and the state began to form in the direction of consumption. The phrase "Hell Society" is frequently used by conservative groups to allude to the "Consumption Society." In Turkey, there is a tradition known as Milli Gorus that stands in opposition to the culture of consumerism as well as the idea of rent. The difference serves as the foundation for the tradition. In this fictitious work, the propensity of individuals to break religious commandments will rise in proportion to the amount of money they spend, and their growing attachment to the world will lead them astray from the correct path.

The visible component of the conflict in Turkey between conservatives who want to decrease consumption and the state that wants to build a current consumption culture has been at the core of the secular-anti-secular headscarf argument in Turkey. Conservatives want to cut consumption, while the state wants to develop a contemporary consumption culture. This disagreement was at the heart of the discussion around the headscarf. This circumstance, the weight of which has been gradually lightened, serves as a model for what should be done.

According to Suleyman Demirel, "There was no power that the pot could not carry" The goal of Westernization in Turkey was to expect a higher level of comfort in day-to-day living and to coerce the Turkish government into meeting these demands. Following the failed coup attempt on July 15, 2016, the administration of the AKP started to marginalize western culture and lifestyles in all aspects of economic, political, and social life in Turkey. Because to Erdogan's leadership, Turkish society has undergone a transformation from one that is demanding to one that is subservient. Congregations, sects, and other nationalist-conservative groups, among others, played an essential part in the process of converting the society into an obedient one by playing an important role in the process.

One of the characteristics of this process that has been called into question is the imitative nature of its modernization. The physician who urges his patients to have 'real dreams' is an example of imitative Westernization in the novel The Time Regulation Institute by Ahmet Hamdi Tanpınar. The fact that Tanpınar has been put in this circumstance demonstrates that they find the imitational, superficial, and phony Westernization to be unsettling. In the well-known short tale "Efruz Bey" by Omer Seyfettin, there is a character who personifies the archetype of the cosmopolitan, Western scientist. According to Bora (2017:72), Western viewers have allowed

CURRENT SCIENCE

themselves to get utterly engrossed in their fixation with programming. This type of modernization is characterized by a passive approach since it merely incorporates the aesthetically pleasing features of Western culture.

During the Tulip Period, the concept of Westernism referred to wearing, living, and having fun in a manner that was reminiscent of the Western world. In contrast, the Tanzimat Period was a time when everything achieved its zenith and was at its most prosperous. A decree that was known as the Tanzimat limited the sultan's authority, which had hitherto been unchecked by any authority. During this period, western styles began to enter into everyday life, not only in politics, but also in literature and entertainment. During this time, western styles began to enter into everyday life. This pattern is now prevalent in every region of the planet. During the reign of Tanzimat, their very own intellectual elite rose to greater prominence.

The administration of the AKP was successful in discouraging the people from participating in the process of westernization, and they founded the state on the basis of this philosophy. There is a long tradition of the military bureaucracy serving as the driving force towards westernization. This custom, which was established with the Union and Progress Revolutions, was carried on into the Republican Revolutions. rule that was severe and dictatorial, which was frequently referred to as military tutelage in Turkey; an economy modeled after that of the West that considered output as essential to the survival of the country. The economic model that was prevalent in the West was predicated on the concept that if production did not take place, the state would be unable to continue to exercise its power, and it would finally fall apart. Because of the way of life and the culture in the West, there will be a rise in the amount of stuff that people buy. This rise in demand will lead to the development of new manufacturing methods, which in turn will lead to the strengthening of the state.

It was a comprehensive paper that spanned 88 pages and was delivered to the Bush administration (Fuller, 1991: 17-44; Henze, 1993: 5-52). This research gave a strategy on how to act based on the thesis that "If Islam and Muslims cannot be harmonized with the values of Western democracy and the global order, there is a high probability of a clash of civilizations." The thesis states that "If Islam and Muslims cannot be harmonized with the values of Western democracy and the global order, there is a high probability of a clash of civilizations." He has dominion over the Islamic lands. The declaration was founded on the notion that "the

CURRENT SCIENCE

probability of a clash of civilizations is high" if Islam and Muslims are not brought into alignment with the principles of Western democracy and the world order. This thought served as the foundation for the statement. Participants in the research come from all across the world, including Muslims and extremists.

Argument

The Report and Book that were just stated are at the forefront of the BOP's strategy to "modernizing the Islamic world" and, as a direct result of this, eliminating worldwide terrorism. Nevertheless, when we take into account the historical indications of traditional US politics, it appears that this objective will not be sufficient; sooner or later, this initiative will become the most essential component of the "Strategy for Control of Eurasia." It was Brzezinski who created the groundwork for this policy, which centered on maintaining U.S. control over important energy supplies and transportation routes in Eurasia. According to him, the primary objective of the United States in Eurasia, which Brzezinski described as resembling a large chessboard, is "to prevent conflicts in Europe, Asia, and the Middle East and the emergence of any other competing superpowers that threaten American interests." (Brzezinski, 1997: 24) Brzezinski's description of Eurasia as a large chessboard provides the foundation for this assumption that he makes.

By maintaining the initiatives that were launched as part of the Eurasian Control framework for the nations of the Islamic geography in the Caucasus, Central Asia, and the Far East, it will be possible to prevent the governments in these regions from assuming a fundamentalist Islamic character or supporting radicals. There is no denying the significance of strategy.

The purpose of the Greater Middle East Project is to fulfill the duty of bringing the western economy and consumer society to the region of the middle east, as well as to ensure the security of Turkey's energy infrastructure and power transmission lines. In addition, the project will fulfill the role of transporting the western economy and consumer society to the region.

During the Greater Middle East Project, Ottomanism was viewed as a fresh form of Kemalism's westernization strategy, the 1923 Republican Revolutions, the global market economy, and westernization ideology. This viewpoint was bolstered by the concept of Neo-Ottomanism as a

CURRENT SCIENCE

contemporary expression of Kemalism. In terms of westernization, Neo-Ottomanism might not be the continuation of the Committee of Union and Progress and the 1923 Republican Revolutions; however, the west encourages production-consumption links. The structure of westernization that produces consuming demand and needs was not desired to be eliminated.

endeavors for westernization in the Ottoman Empire initially came to light and garnered attention during the Tanzimat period. These endeavors began during the period known as "Tajimat." In addition to the Ottoman-Russian wars that took place in the era before this period, the events that were effective in molding the period were the Greek Revolt, the Mehmet Ali Pasha Revolt, and the French Revolution. All of these events took place within this time period. During the time immediately before this time period, the Ottoman Empire was involved in a string of conflicts with Russia. In the history of the Ottoman Empire, the New Ottomans movement may be traced back to the beginning of the formation of independence movements in the western sense. After it, important political organizations like as the Young Turk movement and the Committee of Union and Progress came into being as its successors. The question of whether or not the state should provide protection was the most significant component shared by all of these groups. Although this issue, which should be resolved as soon as possible, hindered the early intellectuals from finding the opportunity to analyze ideological and political concepts, all of the attempts towards Westernization still created a general shift. A different research subject focuses on the mentality problem that existed among the intellectuals of Ottoman society. The intellectuals who came of age during this period were the ones who eventually realized the Republican revolution, which was the zenith of the process that began with the Ottoman Empire. This revolution was the completion of the process that began with the Ottoman empire.

Neo-Ottomanism shifted its attention to Russia's Eurasian policy as a result of the tensions that exist between the Erdogan government and the United States. On the other hand, it is possible to trace its roots all the way back to the Greater Middle East Project, which was headed by the West. Nevertheless, the Erdogan government should not be the only one to attempt to deal with this crisis. Because Turkey's mistrust of the West about its national integrity and security dates back to the 1990s, although it was ineffectual at that time period. However, this mistrust has

CURRENT SCIENCE

been more prevalent in recent years. It is primarily as a result of the fact that the westernization agenda has not been entirely eradicated from the fundamental nature of society and the state.

Since the fall of the Ottoman Empire and the establishment of the contemporary Turkish state, several ideas have been floated as prospective courses of action for Turkey's foreign policy. These policies have been referred to as "potential options." Additionally, there have been several attempts made to realize success through the implementation of policies that are influenced by Turkism, Ottomanism, Westernism, Islamism, and Kemalist philosophy. The word "Neo-Ottomanism" is used to characterize some of the policies that Turkey has embraced in recent years. The growth of an understanding of Eurasianism in recent years can be attributed to the fact that individuals who are opposed to the concept of Turkey's accession to the EU propose Central Asian strategies as an alternative in the realm of foreign policy and believe that Turkish foreign policy ought to be structured within this context. This is what led to the conception of Eurasianist in the first place.

According to Erdogan, Turkey did not require an economy comparable to that of the West, a society that would extend this economy, or, to put it another way, Westernization. It was dismantled along with the 15 July Movement and the Presidential System. Westernization, the Ergenekon-Sledgehammer affair, and other events all had a role. It was previously believed that Turkey had become democratic as a result of the removal of anti-democratic structures. Nevertheless, the Westernization process, which began with the incomprehensible New Ottomans and continued with the Young Turks, Union and Progress, and Six Arrow Republic Revolutions, came to an end on the same day that the Presidential and Parliamentary Elections took place on May 14, 2023. These elections took place on the same day.

The Nation Alliance was left feeling disheartened by the outcome of the General Elections that were held on May 14th, 2023. The reason for this is that it demonstrates that society's detachment from the CHP has transcended westernization and that it has entirely isolated itself from the West in terms of concepts. This is shown by the fact that this situation has occurred. Turkey's departure with westernization; increasing communication between the AKP and churches, sects, and nationalist and nationalist groups. The political arena has seen the emergence of these groups in the shape of continents, which are said to be composed of

CURRENT SCIENCE

individuals who do not demand, do not act with economic aims, are founded on a sense of security, and are prepared to sacrifice themselves when it is required. If they have no other choice, people should eat onions, but the state should strive on producing TOGG, SHA, and UAV instead.

The elections that are scheduled to take place in Turkey on May 14th, 2023 will mark the completion of the country's westernization process. It was the personification of power politics that attempted to drastically reorganize the relationships between the production and consumption of goods in society. To put it another way, the fact that individuals neglect matters such as the state of the economy, threats to national security, and the possibility of their own survival for political reasons demonstrates that they have embraced a new ideological worldview. Throughout the course of the election campaign, the Erdogan Regime made it quite obvious what the unofficial philosophy of its government was. It was discovered that Kemalism, the most recent iteration of the Westernization plan, has lost its status as the key reference point in political discourse as a direct consequence of the elections that were place on May 14, 2023.

With the conclusion of Erdogan's government, the rapprochement with Russia, Iran, China, and the eastern bloc that Erdogan pushed forth in politics would come to an end; it is the forecast that Turkey will revert to the politics it had before Erdogan entered office. This is how Westerners see Turkey, generally speaking.

When Erdogan steps down as president, Turkey will no longer be a country dedicated to westernization, and the Republican People's Party (CHP) will no longer be capable of achieving this objective. The political axis of the CHP is comprised of Westernization, democracy, and modernization politics; national unity, independence; immigration difficulties; xenophobia; and nationalist policies. The continued anti-immigrant policies and the conflict in Kurdistan between the PKK and the Pyd are both expected to have a negative impact on the relationship between the CHP and the West. This has been demonstrated to be true.

If there is a possibility of establishing a Kurdish state in the Middle East, Turkey's dedication to Eurasianism and eventual transition to a complete alliance with Russia will be put to the test. Both of these things will be put to the test. In point of fact, the move to Eurasian-Islamism was

CURRENT SCIENCE

practiced by fully severing ties with the West in response to Turkish society's fears of separation, fragmentation, and the formation of a Kurdish state as a potential danger. This was done in the face of Turkish society's worries about these issues. During the General Elections that took place on May 14th, 2023, these issues were aired.

Even if Erdogan's AKP were to lose power, it appears doubtful that the Republican People's Party would initiate a new project that relates to the fundamental ideological ideals of 1923 and westernization. This is because these beliefs have been discredited. In the elections that were held on May 14, 2023, voters who participated in the demonstrations and voted against Kemal Kılıçdaroglu, the candidate of the Nation Alliance, expressed their concerns regarding the fight against terrorism, the survival of the country, the international situation, and close interaction with HDP. The degree to which Eurasianism exerts its effect on them varies. In the framework of a modernization program that takes into consideration both national security and Eurasian political references, it is impossible for Kemalism and westernization to coexist at the same time.

A growth in the efficacy of religious communities, sects, and nationalist and nationalist organizations in Turkey presents one of the most significant difficulties for westernization as a reference strategy in Turkey. This problem is one of the most crucial ones. After Erdogan's term ends, it does not appear likely that there will be a dramatic shift in the sociology of the closed groups that serve as the foundation of the People's Alliance.

As a result of the right parties' win in the election with 50% of the vote and the consolidation of forces inside the Turkish Presidential System, the right parties are going to even greater lengths to solidify their support bases. The CHP's attempt to win the election by eurasiatizing its platform would result in the adoption of policies that are xenophobic and ultranationalist. Due to the extremism that exists among the social groups in the country within the context of nationalism, it appears to be difficult to execute the growth of westernization as a reference method in Turkish society inside the state. This is the case.

Following the abortive attempt at a coup that took place on July 15, 2016, Eurasianist began to gain prominence in the political sphere in an increasing manner. Both Erdogan's mistrust of the West, which he attributes to his fear of being removed from power, and the Kurdistan

CURRENT SCIENCE

establishment, which he attributes to his fear of PKK terrorism, enhanced each other. Erdogan attributes his mistrust of the West to his fear of being removed from office. In the general elections that took place on May 14, 2023, the government was responsible for organizing the anti-Western opposition. Eurasianism was victorious in its first election, and it was able to defeat the pro-Western Nation Alliance. In the event that Erdogan is removed from power and a Kurdish state is founded in the Middle East, Turkey will fully sever its connections with the West, oppose the embargo and sanctions, and forge an alliance with the Eastern Bloc.

Conclusion

The British Overseas Policy (BOP) seeks to destroy worldwide terrorism and advance modernization throughout the Islamic world. On the other hand, it's possible that this strategy won't be enough in the long term, seeing as how it will become the most essential part of the "Control Strategy of Eurasia." Brzezinski was instrumental in laying the groundwork for this policy, which centered on maintaining U.S. control over critical energy sources and transportation routes located in Eurasia. He asserts that the major objective of the United States' engagement in Eurasia is to forestall the outbreak of war in Europe, Asia, and the Middle East as well as the rise of competing superpowers that pose a risk to the interests of the United States. The purpose of the Greater Middle East Project is to fulfill Turkey's role in bringing the Western economy and consumer society to the region of the Middle East, as well as to secure the safety of Turkey's energy infrastructure and power transmission lines. Both of these goals are being pursued simultaneously. Neo-Ottomanism, a new type of Kemalism, was analyzed as a new version of Kemalism's westernization approach, the origins of which can be traced back to the Greater Middle East Project, which was spearheaded by the West. However, Turkey's mistrust of the West in relation to its national integrity and security dates back to the 1990s. However, at that time, Turkey's mistrust of the West was ineffectual since the Westernization agenda could not be totally eradicated from the essence of society and the state. Since the fall of the Ottoman Empire and the foundation of the contemporary Turkish state, several ideas have been floated as prospective courses of action for Turkey's foreign policy. These ideas come in a broad range of forms. The word "Neo-Ottomanism" is used to characterize some of Turkey's more recent policies. In recent years, there has been a growth in comprehension of the concept of Eurasianist. This may be linked to the fact that those who are opposed to the concept of Turkey's

CURRENT SCIENCE

membership in the EU advocate for Central Asian strategies in foreign policy as an alternative and feel that Turkey's foreign policy should be formed in this framework. Erdogan asserted that Turkey did not require an economic system that was comparable to that of the West, a society that would contribute to the expansion of this economic system, or, in a nutshell, westernization. Along with the 15 July Movement and the Presidential System, Westernization, the Ergenekon-Sledgehammer affair, and other events were put down. It was generally accepted that the eradication of anti-democratic structures in Turkey was the primary factor in the country's subsequent democratic transformation. The process of Westernization, which began with the uralitizing New Ottomans and continued through the Young Turks, Union and Progress, and Six Arrow Republic Revolutions, came to a close with the Presidential and Parliamentary Elections on May 14, 2023. This marked the conclusion of the Westernization process. The results of the General Elections that were held on May 14, 2023 were disheartening for the Nation Alliance because they show that the distance of the society from the CHP has transcended westernization and has totally moved away from the West in terms of concepts. This was a result that proved that the CHP is no longer the dominant ideology in the society. The detachment of Turkey from Westernization and the accelerated engagement of communities, sects, nationalists, and nationalist groups with the AKP shown that people neglect problems such as political motivations, the economic circumstances, the national security situation, and the matter of survival. During the course of the election campaign, the Erdogan Regime made the unofficial philosophy that guided it extremely evident to everyone. Kemalism, the most recent iteration of the Westernization policy, has lost its status as the major reference point in political discourse as a direct consequence of the elections that took place on May 14, 2023. It is anticipated that Turkey will return to politics before Erdogan enters office, which would put an end to the rapprochement with Russia, Iran, China, and the eastern bloc that Erdogan put forth in politics. The end of Erdogan's administration will also bring an end to the government itself. When Erdogan leaves office, Turkey will no longer be able to make a commitment to westernization, and the CHP will no longer be capable of achieving this objective. The CHP views westernization, democracy, the policy of modernization, national unity, independence, immigration difficulties, xenophobia, and nationalist policies as the axis of its political platform. It is possible that the relationship between the CHP and the West will suffer as a result of the continuous anti-immigrant measures in Kurdistan and the conflict that exists between the PKK and the Pyd. Whether or if Turkey has the ability to build a Kurdish state in the Middle East will be a test of its commitment to Eurasianism and, eventually, to a

CURRENT SCIENCE

complete alliance with Russia. The Republican People's Party was able to complete its shift to Eurasian-Islamism by severing ties with the West in spite of Turkish society's fears about separation, fragmentation, and the establishment of a Kurdish state. This was done in response to the RPP's desire to establish a Kurdish state. It is possible for xenophobia and ultranationalist policies to emerge as a result of the consolidation of the presidential system and an election victory with at least 50% of the vote. The extremism that exists within social groups within the context of nationalism makes it appear as though it will be impossible to put into practice the emergence of westernization as a reference method in Turkish society. After the failed coup attempt on July 15, 2016, Eurasianism entered the political arena as Erdogan's mistrust of the West and the Kurdistan establishment strengthened each other. Eurasianism is a political ideology that emphasizes the importance of Eurasia. Eurasianism was victorious in its first election, which took place on May 14, 2023, and defeated the pro-Western Nation Alliance to become the dominant political ideology. The government was responsible for organizing the anti-Western opposition in these elections. Turkey will cut its connections with the West, resist the embargo and sanctions, and forge an alliance with the Eastern Bloc if Erdogan is removed from power and a Kurdish state is formed in the Middle East.

Resources

<https://uliwiki.org/index.php?title=Avrasyac%C4%B1%C4%B1k>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tun%C3%A7er_K%C4%B1%C4%B1n%C3%A7

<https://medyascope.tv/2020/05/29/turkiyede-avrasyacilik-rusen-cakir-omer-taspinar-ve-suat-kiniklioğlu-tartisiyor/>

<https://www.odatv4.com/guncel/erdoganin-cevresinde-avrasyaci-ekip-2212161200-106160>

"Turkey is divided within itself" ACADEMIC THINKING INSTITUTE - Copyright 2017 - 2022 / ISSN: 2687-6310

https://tasam.org/Files/Icerik/File/turk_avrasyasi_ve_avrasyaciligi_uzerine_4c8cf535-6db9-4ab8-87ab-6e00f2f1e8ce.pdf

Sebile DEMIRCI, The Concept of Westernization in the Ottoman Empire and the Attitudes of Ottoman Intellectuals to Westernization

Altu GÜNAL, GREAT MIDDLE EAST PROJECT AND TURKEY, Research Assistant Ege University Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences Department of International Relations altug.gunal@ege.edu.tr

<https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/556861> (GREAT MIDDLE

EAST PROJECT AND TURKEY

Barış DEMİRTAŞ, Utah University Faculty of Arts and Sciences Journal of Social Sciences

Vol: 8, Issue: 13, Page: 2007/2, Author: Westernization Movements in the Ottoman

Empire in the Context of Young Turks